

BEYOND BAD APPLES: The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

Research integrity
BEYOND bad apples
A European consortium
including three thematic networks

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BEYOND BAD APPLES: Towards a Behavioral and Evidence-Based Approach to Promote Research Ethics and Research Integrity in Europe

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Abbreviations

DEC: Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication; FFP: Falsification, Fabrication, & Plagiarism; HEI: Higher Education Institution; QRP: Questionable Research Practices; RDI: Research, Development and Innovation; RE/RI: Research Ethics and Research Integrity; RFO: Research Funding Organization; R&I: Research and Innovation; RM: Research Misconduct; RPO: Research Performing Organization (including both pure research organizations and higher education institutions)

Disclaimer

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1. Executive summary of BEYOND

The main mission of BEYOND is to increase trust in science as a foundation for an inclusive, open, and democratic society. BEYOND will reinforce ongoing efforts to reform and enhance the European R&I system by developing, disseminating, and embedding evidence-based regulatory and educational outputs that support adherence to the highest standards of RE/RI and in doing so prevent research misconduct (RM) and questionable research practices (QRPs).

The main stakeholder groups include all members of the research ecosystem (RPOs and RFOs, RE/RI officers, and the research community). Other stakeholder groups include representatives of RDI management in industry, civil society, and policymakers. The project will support RPOs, researchers, and RFOs in improving research environments and fostering supportive RE/RI cultures that assign individual and institutional responsibilities for RM prevention and allow researchers to flourish.

Multiple access points to key stakeholder networks and a strong dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy put BEYOND in an excellent position to accomplish widespread uptake of project results, thus enhancing the quality, relevance, robustness, accessibility, and dissemination of research.

By promoting operationally viable measures to support a generalised, and consistently high level of RE/RI, BEYOND will increase the reliability, transparency, and trustworthiness of research processes and consequently strengthen the relationship between science and society.

2. Introduction of the DEC plan

This first version of the DEC plan outlines the dissemination, exploitation and communication plan of BEYOND. The DEC plan will be updated as the work towards project deliverables proceeds and the most efficient strategies and activities to promote them have been established. The updated DEC plan is due at the end of 2023 as Deliverable 7.2.

The key factors in determining the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities and channels for BEYOND are the project deliverables and milestones, along with the needs of stakeholder groups, with project resources factored in. The goal of all communication and dissemination is to enhance the exploitability of project results.

Communication activities provide information about the project to stakeholders who are specialists and a wider non-specialist audience throughout the lifespan of the project.

Dissemination activities make project results public, particularly to stakeholders and policymakers but also to citizens, to maximize the impact of the project and widen the scope of exploitation by new stakeholder groups and potential end-users of the project deliverables.

Exploitation activities are focused on the end stage of the project. The purpose of exploitation is the efficient use of project results for knowledge transfer, in policymaking, and by stakeholders.

2.1 Deliverables and Milestones

The communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategies and activities of BEYOND derive from the deliverables and milestones of the project. Milestones include DEC activities, for example events organised, and the progress towards project deliverables. All the public milestones and deliverables, once approved by the reviewers, will be made available on the project page of BEYOND in the community section of The Embassy of Good Science.

The deliverables and milestones of BEYOND are listed below. The DEC channels and activities best suited for specific deliverables and milestones will be included in the updated DEC plan (D7.2).

Table 1. Deliverables and Milestones of BEYOND

Year 2023		
Month	Deliverable	Milestone
M1-M5	Stakeholder identification and awareness-raising	
M2		M7.1 BEYOND branding and logo
M3	D7.1 Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication of Results	
M5		M7.2 Communications activity launch

M6	D2.1 Consultation paper/plan to engage the public and expert stakeholders D8.1 Data Management Plan D8.2 Ethics Management Plan	M1.1 Completion of the literature review M2.1 List of stakeholders and recruitment plan M8.1 Stakeholder Advisory Board established
M9		M2.2 Functioning electronic platform for public consultation
M10	D1.2 Systematic review of RM validated instruments D6.1 Strategy for the development of supplementary trainer guide and new training materials and tools	M7.3 Cross-SwafS workshop 1 in ENRIO Congress 2023, Paris
M12	D1.1 Insights from the literature review and review of cases D7.2 Updated Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication of Results D7.3 Policy Briefing 1	M3.1 Model of selective reporting behaviours and a systematic overview of potential nudging interventions for change M8.2 Stakeholder advisory board coordination

Year 2024		
Month	Deliverable	Milestone
M14		M4.1 Identification and implementation of selected measurement methods

M20		M2.3 Workshop for analysis of preliminary results of public consultation M4.2 Designing principles for large-scale feasible measurement in a short, medium, and long-term perspective
M21	D2.2 Report on the results of the BEYOND public consultation	
M22	D6.2 Report on supplementary trainer guide and new training materials on RE/RI	
M23	D4.1 Report on the methodologies and measurements explored, and guidelines including functionality,	
Year 2024		
	feasibility and reliability of each method for the assessment of training initiatives and interventions in RI	

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M24	<p>D3.1 Report on contextually sensitive framework for defining QRPs, including nudges D3.2 Report on tackling QRPs through contextual interventions D4.2 Large-scale feasible measurement instruments on short, medium and long-term training effects adapted to the needs of a variety of target groups and different fields/domains</p>	
M21-36	<p>Dissemination activities:</p> <p>M21-M36 BEYOND online training sessions M21-M36 BEYOND university partners M21-M36 Training courses M21-M36 Engagement events M21-M36 Conferences & workshops (World Congress on Research Integrity 2024) M21-M36 "Beyond Bad Apples" webinars M21-M36 Scientific publications</p>	

Year 2025		
Month	Deliverable	Milestone
M25		<p>M6.1 Training materials and tools available on Embassy of Good Science and integrated into ENERI Classroom</p>
M34	<p>D6.3 Report on pilot-tests of training materials and tools</p>	

M35	D5.1 Guidelines D5.2 Best practice manual D5.3 2030 Roadmap	
M36	D7.4 Policy Briefing 2	M6.2 Final version of training materials and tools available on Embassy of Good Science and integrated into ENERI Classroom

The exploitation activities extend beyond the end of the project in M36.

Specific dissemination channels and materials will be identified for all key deliverables in the updated DEC plan. Tables 2-4 below present the preliminary plan for DEC activities.

2.2 Stakeholders

The identification of stakeholders, stakeholder needs, and their preferred ways of engagement inform the planning and scheduling of communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. Stakeholder engagement feeds into all DEC activities.

The stakeholder recruitment plan (M2.1) and the establishment of the Stakeholder Advisory Board (M8.1) in June 2023 will guide the discussion with stakeholders and help determine the best channels and methods of communication with them. Stakeholders are recruited into the stakeholder board by efficient, diverse and inclusive means. Stakeholder engagement guides the development of specific deliverables (e.g., a best practice manual, roadmap, training materials), placing particularly specialist stakeholders in a position to contribute also to the respective DEC strategies in question.

The five key stakeholder groups of BEYOND as specified in the project plan are 1) the research community, 2) RPOs and RFOs, 3) policymakers, 4) RE/RI committees and officers, and 5) citizens.

The research ecosystem is the target audience for BEYOND's initiatives, given that all stakeholders benefit from an improved RE/RI culture. This ecosystem includes actors and organisations in a position to implement policies, guidelines, and training materials: RPOs, RFOs, HEIs, research ethics committees, research integrity offices and officers, educators, and research publishers. Through horizontal coordination and the involvement of The Embassy of Good Science, acting as a central community hub for RE/RI projects and initiatives, BEYOND will liaise with other relevant EC funded projects for purposes of colearning, efficient DEC activities, and good use of project resources in all projects.

In the broader social sphere, BEYOND participates in public discourse on research integrity to strengthen social trust in science and research. Stakeholder groups include the general public, civil society organisations, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs).

The Stakeholder Advisory Board links the BEYOND consortium to the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities, ALLEA (the curator of the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity), ENRIO, EARMA, UNESCO (specifically the Bureau of the Intergovernmental Bioethics Committee), the European Network for Academic Integrity, EUfunded projects (e.g. Path2Integrity), and other European and international institutions and stakeholder groups.

3. Communication

Communication activities are targeted at all stakeholders, including the general public, to ensure the effective dissemination and exploitation of project outcomes. This work takes place throughout the lifespan of BEYOND.

The aims of communication activities are:

- to inform citizens (broadly defined as the general public, including members of nonspecialist audience) in an accessible and inviting style about the aims and activities of projects under the auspices of Horizon-Europe funding;
- to establish the credibility of responsible research among the general public, generating exposure and visibility of BEYOND for citizens;
- to raise awareness among the specialist stakeholder groups about the stakes of BEYOND, project advancement, activities, and the delivery of its results.

The main communication channels are the project website, social media, and The Embassy of Good Science. The general public can also be reached through media collaboration.

The **BEYOND website** (due in M7) will be the public face of the project. The website provides information about the objectives, activities, progress, and results of BEYOND as well as the project partners. Website publications go hand in hand with social media activities in that website content (news articles, event information, updated deliverable lists) will always be promoted in the project's social media channels. Project partners determine which website functionalities best serve the project's interests and resources.

Twitter and LinkedIn are the **social media platforms** most likely to be used by specialist stakeholders. Project partners decide whether BEYOND accounts will be created on both platforms. Other prospective channels for social media engagement include stakeholder accounts and the accounts of project partners and their organisations. BEYOND's content can thus be shared, and BEYOND's partners can participate in discussions in three actor-specific social media channels. Effective social media activity requires commitment from all BEYOND project partners.

The use of social media channels and the identification of other relevant channels of communication are established in project-internal discussions. The best use of project resources is evaluated to ascertain that resources are directed efficiently.

The website and social media channels will be launched in May 2023.

Project partners will follow and participate in topical discussions on RM and QRPs in order to foster discussion and present novel perspectives in the public sphere. Possible channels include social media, The Embassy of Good Science, stakeholder events and media collaboration.

Table 2. Provisional communication plan

Stakeholders	Purpose	Channel	Material	WP in charge
RPOs/RFOs Research community RE/RI officers Citizens	Informing of the aims and advances of BEYOND Raising awareness Improving trust in European science	Engagement events	TBD	WP2
RPOs/RFOs Research community RE/RI officers Citizens	Informing of the aims and advances of BEYOND Raising awareness Improving trust in European science	Project website The Embassy of Good Science Newsletter Media Social media	Project description, articles, news, events Promotion of all project activities Bi-annual content Press releases, news articles, op-eds Twitter, LinkedIn	WP7, with all WPs

As the interests of the **general public** differ from those of the specialist stakeholder groups, part of the communication strategy is to identify what specific non-specialist groups the project intends to reach, which deliverables and project activities are best suited for these communication activities, and what communication channels serve best in this work.

4. Dissemination

Dissemination activities target all stakeholders in the research ecosystem. The purpose of dissemination activities is to maximise the impact of the project and promote RE/RI in relevant stakeholder platforms.

Stakeholders will contribute to the DEC activities of BEYOND. Several BEYOND partners and key European networks will engage, according to their specifics, in the dissemination activities, leveraging their own networks and identifying opportunities. In addition, dissemination relies on European networks dedicated to RE/RI or the organisation of the European R&I system, which will facilitate contextualisation of the dissemination material, for instance adaptation to vernacular languages.

As members of the BEYOND consortium, **three major European networks**, namely ENRIO, EUREC (representing ENERI) and The Guild of European Research-Intensive Universities, act as dissemination and embedding partners. BEYOND will also create a sustainable community on **The Embassy of Good Science** for the sharing and adaptation of project outcomes by the research community and specialist stakeholders. In addition, several members of the consortium are members of **the Network for Education in Research Quality (NERQ)**, launched as a follow-up of H2020 projects on RI education and training and supported by the European Commission. These networks and other key stakeholder groups will integrate project outputs into their working practices, update them if necessary after the end of BEYOND, and also disseminate updates in their communities.

Some work packages include engagement with **trainees and research participants**, especially the intervention and measurement activities in WP3 and WP4. This type of project participation is also an opportunity to communicate about and disseminate the BEYOND message.

All the resources produced by the project (including training materials, webinars, guidelines, and policy briefs) and the events and conferences organised and attended by the project will be promoted and disseminated through the project website, social media channels, and The Embassy of Good Science. The table below presents a breakdown of other dissemination channels used to disseminate project activities.

Table 3. Provisional dissemination plan

Target stakeholder groups	Purpose of DEC	Channels	Materials	WP in charge
Research community	Dissemination to Promote RE/RI in daily R&I activities	BEYOND online training sessions for stakeholders	Training materials and tools, with stewardship	WP6
	Liaise with other ECfunded projects or RFOs	BEYOND RPO partners	Training materials and tools, with stewardship	WP6

		Training courses available through project website and The Embassy of Good Science	Training materials and tools	WP6
		Stakeholder engagement events	Engagement and discussion	WP2
		Conferences and workshops	Presentations, posters and conference workshops	WP7, WP3
		Beyond Bad Apples webinars, available through project website and The Embassy of Good Science	Focused oral presentations and facilitated discussions	WP7
		Scientific publications and stakeholder publications (e.g., ENRIO's <i>RIPE</i>)	Peer-reviewed publications, articles in specialised journals	WP1, WP3, WP4
		Project website and newsletter	Articles, background information, policy briefs, event information	WP7
		Social media	Twitter, LinkedIn feeds	WP7
		Beyond Bad Apples webinars	Focused oral presentations and facilitated discussions	WP7
		The Embassy of Good Science		
	<p>Dissemination to</p> <p>Promote RE/RI at the organisational level, including by shifting RPOs and RFOs* incentives to avoid unfortunate side-effects</p> <p>Promote and deliver appropriate training</p>	Horizontal coordination in thematic networks	Guidelines, best practice manual, 2030 Roadmap, nudges	WP3, WP5
		Project website	Articles, background information, newsletter, policy briefs	WP7
		Project website	Twitter, LinkedIn feeds	WP7
		Social media	Twitter, LinkedIn feeds	WP7
RE/RI officers	Dissemination to	Beyond Bad Apples webinars	Focused oral presentations and facilitated discussions	WP7

Promote RE/RI in local R&I systems and international networks	The Embassy of Good Science	Guidelines, best practice manual, 2030 roadmap, nudges	WP3, WP5
	Horizontal coordination in thematic networks		
	Project website	Methodologies to evaluate the impact of RM/QRP	WP4
* The different roles of RPOs and RFOs in the research ecosystem will be noted in DEC activities and the updated DEC plan (D7.2).	Open-access scientific publications and stakeholder publications (e.g., ENRIO's <i>RIPE</i>)	Peer-reviewed publications, articles in specialised journals	WP1, WP3, WP4, WP7
	Stakeholder conferences and events (ENRIO Congress 2023, EARMA 2024+2025, WCRI 2024)	Presentations, posters and conference workshops	

5. Exploitation

The exploitation work focuses on delivering the project results for wide use among the stakeholders. Exploitation will proceed through knowledge transfer, using training materials and tools, and the enrichment of public policymaking, targeting particularly RE/RI officers. Exploitation efforts are not expected to follow commercial routes.

The main exploitation tools that will be used to promote RE/RI in future RD policies are training materials and tools, the guidelines, the best practice manual, and the 2030 Roadmap.

The target audience for exploitation consists of the researcher community, research managers, teachers in HEIs and other trainers, RI officers, members of ethics committees, and science communicators.

Table 4. Provisional exploitation plan

Target stakeholder groups	Purpose of DEC	Channels	Material	WP in charge
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<p>Policy makers</p> <p>Exploitation to</p> <p>Promote RE/RI in future R&I policies</p>	The Embassy of Good Science	Guidelines, best practice manual, 2030 roadmap, training materials and tools	WP5
	Project website		
	The Embassy of Good Science	Policy briefs	WP7
	Project website		

7. Channels, materials and tools

Website and visual design

The project website is the main communication channel for BEYOND. It serves as a hub where all project-related information on deliverables can be found. The project website provides stakeholder groups with information on the advancements, results, and deliverables of BEYOND, in an accessible and visually engaging form. All relevant content will be actively promoted on social media.

The visual design services will be outsourced. The visual design includes the project logo, typography, colour scheme, and graphic elements. The existing visual design created for the project proposal will be used as a basis for the work so that the communications budget is used efficiently.

Social media

The social media presence of BEYOND is threefold and consists of 1) the project's own social media account(s), 2) dissemination through the accounts of project partners and their organisations, and 3) dissemination through stakeholder accounts. The project is envisioned to start with a Twitter and LinkedIn presence.

The impact of social media presence is increased by building and fostering brand ownership of BEYOND. Project partners and select specialist stakeholders are encouraged (with guidance) to actively manage BEYOND's brand by sharing content on their respective channels.

Social media engagement must include both the dissemination of BEYOND content as well as participation in and contributions to stakeholder discussions, with a community-building give-and-take approach.

Events

Project partners will organise BEYOND-focused events and activities, as BEYOND Bad Apples webinars. Partners will participate in activities identified as relevant for the project aims and/or that are organised by stakeholders, for example conferences.

Newsletter

The BEYOND newsletter will serve as a tool for stakeholder engagement strategy. The newsletter informs specialist stakeholders about upcoming events, milestones, and accomplished deliverables. Newsletter content draws largely from articles and news on the BEYOND website, with links to other relevant sites. It will be sent out twice a year, with flexibility to change the schedule in order to share significant project outcomes.

WP7 coordinates the newsletter production, maintains the subscriber list as per GDPR regulations, and creates a data management plan for the newsletter.

The Embassy of Good Science

BEYOND will create sustainable participation in the Embassy of Good Science for stakeholders in the entire research community. By making the project outcomes available via The Embassy of Good Science, BEYOND will a) ensure the long-term availability of its results, b) allow stakeholders to engage with the materials by suggesting adaptations and sharing experiences, and c) ensure dissemination of the outcomes towards a broader audience and established community of users.

Outcomes of the project will be presented on the dedicated BEYOND project page and in the different sections of the platform, depending on the type of material. The training materials will be presented in the training section of the platform, where a dedicated page will be created.

The Wiki nature of the platform will allow trainers and users to reuse the materials according to their needs and to create their own trainings by adapting and combining the resources created by BEYOND and other resources available on the platform, thereby fostering crosspollination between the results of different projects and integration of the new material into a broader collection of training resources.

ENRIO bulletin *Research Integrity Practice in Europe*

The upcoming stakeholder publication *Research Integrity Practice in Europe* (RIPE), published by ENRIO and edited by project consortium member (TENK), will be launched in 2023. RIPE publishes informative web articles on the practical aspects of RI for research integrity officers in Europe, and as a specialist publication it can be used as a dissemination channel for BEYOND. The WP7 leader of BEYOND is the Lead Editor of *RIPE*.

Videos, infographics and other audio-visual channels

Videos and infographics provide information in an easily accessible and easily disseminated form for both specialist and non-specialist stakeholders. Their inclusion in the DEC plan will be decided based on project resources.

Media

Media cooperation improves the efficiency of communication activities targeted particularly at the general public. These activities include press releases and pitching stories and features to the media. BEYOND partners can also promote the project in suitable podcasts. Press

releases can be used for reports, guides, policy briefs, and other project results. Media analysis and target group analysis are required for efficient media activities.

8. Key Performance Indicators

To ensure the effectiveness of DEC activities, a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be implemented. The KPIs for BEYOND will include the following:

BEYOND Website: Monitoring website traffic and downloads of reports and other publications. The analytics service will be provided by Matomo Analytics. The aim is to increase visits to the website through disseminating information in social media channels and other relevant channels.

BEYOND Social Media activity:

KPIs for social media will be decided when the social media platforms are selected. The aim will be to keep the followers that BEYOND attracts and increase the number of followers over the course of the project.

BEYOND Newsletter: The newsletter is used to measure the number of interested stakeholders. Newsletter provider Gruppo tracks the number of people who have subscribed to the newsletter, the number of people who have opened the newsletter, and the country where the newsletter is accessed. The aim is to keep the subscribers who sign up and to increase the number of subscribers so that the newsletter reaches a geographically broad audience in Europe and beyond.

Articles: Project partners decide whether BEYOND aims to publish a specific number of peer-reviewed articles in academic journals, non-peer-reviewed articles in other publications, or other types of publications. This metric can be tracked with acceptance rates and the number of published pieces.

Media: Policy briefs, reports and other project results can be accompanied by press releases. Features in media can be used as metrics in monitoring the efficiency of DEC activities, particularly (but not exclusively) for the general audience.

Webinars, training events and engagement events: The organization of and participation in events are tracked. Project partners report the number of attendees in the events they organise.

The Embassy of Good Science: Platform traffic and interactions with BEYOND project materials, including the number of adaptations of the training materials, can be tracked through the maintenance page of the platform. At the moment, the platform engages a community of over 400 trainers across 32 countries in Europe and beyond.

10. Project-internal communication and reporting

BEYOND project partners uses the Microsoft Teams platform for project-internal communication. The University of Oslo provides access to the platform.

Project leaders have monthly meetings online, and WP partners determine the channels and methods of communication that best serve them. Project-internal communications practices will be established by WP7 and WP8 together with project partners to ensure an efficient flow of information.

All project participants will be updated about project reports, milestones, and deliverables. These outcomes will be stored in a dedicated repository of the Embassy of Good Science. The purpose of the repository is to ensure that all project participants have access to all outcomes throughout the project's lifespan. Shared knowledge is crucial in managing interconnected work packages, as pictured in the PERT chart below.

Figure 1. BEYOND PERT Chart

A list of DEC channels (events, networks, publications) will be maintained in Teams (WP7). This list provides information for project partners and helps schedule dissemination and communication activities.

10.1 Reporting

Continuous reporting of communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities to the European Commission is required throughout the course of the project. For dissemination and exploitation activities, project consortia are required to continue reporting after the project has ended.

This section explains how to fulfil the reporting criteria specified by the Funding and Tender portal for BEYOND project partners. The report spreadsheet in Teams is filled out in accordance with the guidelines below:

- **Communication reporting:** all partners report their Press and Media, Events and Publication activities every three months ["3 monthly"?)

- **Dissemination reporting:** all partners report their Press and Media, Events and Publication activities every six months ["6 monthly"]
- **Exploitation of results:** all partners report exploitation activities every six months or at the latest in the periodic reporting, focusing on the contents of the results
- **Press and Media details:** all partners report any external mentions of the project
- **Scientific publication:** all partners report scientific publications at the time of publication

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